

Gene and Protein Virtual Lab

In this Lab (<https://gplab.diff.org/>), the effect of amino acid availability as regulating factor of every protein synthesis is investigated

Gene and Protein Virtual Lab Home Protein Chromosomes

Human Chromosomes

Gene/Protein Tables from Uniprot and

Chromosome number: y

	Gene stable ID	Gene name	Gene start (bp)	Gene end (bp)	id length	entry name	A	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	K	L	M	N	P	Q	R	S	T	
34	ENSG00000184895	SRY	2786855	2787682	Q05066	204	SRY_HUMAN	15	6	9	12	5	4	5	4	15	16	9	12	13	14	18	21	6
18	ENSG00000129824	RPS4Y1	2841602	2932000	P22090	263	RS4Y1_HUMAN	14	4	14	9	11	24	9	21	26	19	5	11	13	3	22	8	17
10	ENSG00000067646	ZFY	2935281	2982506	P08048	801	ZFY_HUMAN	45	33	68	71	23	36	56	46	67	42	22	23	33	29	28	58	37
17	ENSG00000176679	TGIF2LY	3579067	3580041	Q8IUE0	185	TF2LY_HUMAN	18	4	8	12	2	7	5	8	15	12	6	8	15	11	17	17	9
39	ENSG00000099715	PCDH11Y	5000226	5742224	Q9BZA8	1340	PC11Y_HUMAN	83	19	88	75	46	61	37	86	60	113	19	79	97	54	46	120	100
19	ENSG00000168757	TSPY2	6246223	6249019	A6NKD2	308	TSPY2_HUMAN	30	4	10	39	10	16	8	10	12	25	10	12	16	15	25	20	9
37	ENSG00000099721	AMELY	6865918	6911774	Q99218	206	AMELY_HUMAN	11	1	4	5	5	8	14	9	3	20	9	4	42	27	5	9	8
25	ENSG00000092377	TBL1Y	6910686	7101970	Q9BQ87	522	TBL1Y_HUMAN	44	11	31	25	17	39	19	30	24	35	13	30	22	24	12	56	32
35	ENSG00000099725	PRKY	7273972	7381548	O43930	277	PRKY_HUMAN	23	4	14	21	18	18	12	14	16	27	8	5	17	6	16	14	13
41	ENSG00000233803	TSPY4	9337464	9340284	P0CV99	314	TSPY4_HUMAN	31	4	10	41	11	16	8	10	12	25	10	12	17	15	24	19	9
6	ENSG00000229549	TSPY8	9357797	9360599	P0CW00	308	TSPY8_HUMAN	30	4	10	39	11	16	8	10	12	26	10	12	16	15	23	19	9
38	ENSG00000228927	TSPY3	9398421	9401223	P0CV98	308	TSPY3_HUMAN	30	4	10	39	11	16	8	10	12	25	10	12	17	15	24	19	9
42	ENSG00000258992	TSPY1	9466955	9469749	Q01534	308	TSPY1_HUMAN	30	4	10	38	11	17	8	10	12	24	10	12	18	15	24	19	9
36	ENSG00000236424	TSPY10	9527880	9530682	P0CW01	308	TSPYA_HUMAN	30	4	10	39	11	16	8	10	12	25	10	12	17	15	24	19	9
28	ENSG00000114374	USP9Y	12537650	12860839	O00507	2555	USP9Y_HUMAN	159	61	157	176	104	128	75	154	138	293	56	139	124	135	123	172	97
22	ENSG00000067048	DDX3Y	12904108	12920478	O15523	660	DDX3Y_HUMAN	35	8	47	41	29	79	15	32	33	47	14	25	27	20	55	64	24

The local availability of amino acids (AA) may be a limiting factor in protein biosynthesis.

Knowing that a number of proteins have a similar content of the same AA means to be able to predict that the expression of these proteins will depend on the same environmental conditions controlling AA availability. From this consideration arises the need to create a tool capable of quickly calculating the AA content of proteins and compare groups of protein based on their AA content. The information gleaned from this comparison may help to solve many biological and biochemical questions.

The studies based on the principle

Based on this approach, we carried out some research focused on AA composition of human proteins. The first study compared human proteins on the basis of their AA content by a hierarchical, agglomerative clustering method. Proteins with similar tissue expression, even though with different function, were very close in the cluster, and this was suggestive that the local availability of AAs was a major driver of protein expression, conditioned by tissue context (Vernone 2013). (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3617222/>) Moreover, in a second study we calculated the absolute and the relative frequencies of all AA contained in the proteins expressed selectively by distinct cellular populations. Our analysis demonstrated that the estimation of glutamate/glutamine ratio can give information on tissue oxygenation. Interestingly, this study suggested that the similar content in single AAs of proteins codified by the same chromosome could be one of the reasons for gene clustering (Vernone 2019). (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6502398/>)

Further studies

The relationship between gene clustering and AA content of human proteins warrants further studies, which require the knowledge of both position in chromosome and AA content of the proteins. The position of the codifying gene becomes relevant when analysing common features of groups of proteins, such as amino acid content, in gene clusters, loci or other specific regions of human chromosomes. To perform this analysis there is a need for a **bioinformatics tool able to provide details on the position of the codifying gene and on the AA sequence and length of the translated protein.**

HERE AND NOW: PROTEIN ANALYSIS TOOL, CHROMOSOME ANALYSIS TOOL

In **PROTEIN section**, a tool has been created with the aim of calculating the AA content of proteins and compare groups of protein based on their AA content. In **CHROMOSOME section**, a tool has been created with the aim of providing lists of proteins based on the position of their codifying gene, also supplying the AA sequence and length of the translated protein.

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the 'Gene and Protein Virtual Lab' website. The URL in the address bar is 'gplab.diff.org/contributors'. The page has a blue header with the site name and navigation links for 'Home', 'Protein', and 'Chromosomes'. A search bar is located in the top right corner. On the left side, there is a sidebar menu with links for 'Overview', 'Contributors', 'Research Papers', and 'Flipper Link'. The main content area features the title 'Gene and Protein Virtual Lab' and a subtitle: 'In this Lab, the effect of amino acid availability as regulating factor of every protein synthesis is investigated'. Below this, there is a list of contributors, each in a separate box:

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